

Cellular Automata and Discrete Complex Systems

24th IFIP WG 1.5 International Workshop, AUTOMATA 2018
Ghent, Belgium, June 20-22, 2018
Exploratory Papers

Editors

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Preface

The 24th International Workshop on Cellular Automata and Discrete Complex Systems (AUTOMATA 2018) was held in Ghent, Belgium, during June 20–22, 2018. It was organized by the Research Unit Knowledge-based Systems of the Department of Data Analysis and Mathematical Modelling of Ghent University. The event was an IFIP Working Conference and it hosted the annual meeting of the IFIP Working Group 1.5.

AUTOMATA 2018 continued an annual series of events established in 1995. In particular, the aims of the workshops are:

- To establish and maintain a permanent, international, multidisciplinary forum for the collaboration of researchers in the field of Cellular Automata (CA) and Discrete Complex Systems (DCS).
- To provide a platform for presenting and discussing new ideas and results.
- To support the development of theory and applications of CA and DCS (for example, parallel computing, physics, biology, social sciences, and others) as long as fundamental aspects and their relations are concerned.
- To identify and study within an inter- and multidisciplinary context, the important fundamental aspects, concepts, notions and problems concerning CA and DCS.

This volume contains the full papers of AUTOMATA 2018. We would like to thank the invited speakers

- Henryk Fukś (Brock University, St. Catharines, Canada)
- Andrew Adamatzky (University of the West of England, Bristol, United Kingdom)
- Michael Schreckenberg (Universität Duisburg-Essen, Duisburg, Germany)

for accepting the invitations and presenting us several diverse perspectives on CA.

There were 12 exploratory papers submitted to AUTOMATA 2018 by a total of 37 authors from all over the world. Each submission was evaluated by three or four Program Committee members. Based on the reviews and discussions, the committee decided to accept 11 exploratory papers to be presented at the conference and to be included in the local proceedings. We would like to thank all authors for their contributions and work without which this event would not have been possible.

We warmly thank the members of the Program Committee for their excellent work in making this selection. We also thank the additional external reviewers for their careful evaluation. All these efforts were the basis for the success of the workshop. We are also grateful to the remaining members of the local Organizing Committee, Aisling Daly, Bernard De Baets, Jan Roels, Renaud Lambiotte, Ruth Van den Driessche, and Tim Depraetere. Finally, we are indebted to all participants for attending the workshop. We hope that this workshop will be a successful and fruitful meeting, will bear new ideas for investigations, and will bring together people for new scientific collaborations.

June 20, 2018

Jan M. Baetens
Martin Kutrib

Organization

AUTOMATA 2018 was organized by the Research Unit Knowledge-based Systems of the Department of Data Analysis and Mathematical Modelling of Ghent University. The conference took place at the Ghent University Conference Centre Het Pand.

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A family of network automata based on neighborhood density

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Abstract. The rule space of some families of cellular automata (CA) can be huge, which makes them computationally difficult to explore and investigate CA dynamics. The same challenge applies to CAs that are embedded into irregular topologies, like networks. The number of states and the size of the neighborhood are among the properties that directly influence the rule space. In this work, we introduce a family of network automata for which the transition function uses the neighborhood density of the given cells to define their states during the automaton evolution. We investigate how the neighborhood density can be partitioned and how these partitions are influenced by the connectivity of the underlying network.

Keywords: Network automata · Cellular automata · Network analysis.

1 Introduction

For many families of cellular automata (CA), the rule space is too vast to be explored computationally. Neither is possible to efficiently extract relevant information from it [5, 10]. Consider, for instance, the family of the classic Life-like CA. This CA family, defined on a 2-dimensional grid using the Moore neighborhood, offers 2^{18} possible rules, i.e., 262,144 rules. Going from the elementary CAs (ECAs) to 3-state totalistic CAs, the number of rules increases dramatically.

The rule space does not only depend on the number of states or on the size of the neighborhood, but also on specific properties such as the neighborhood structure (e.g., Moore or von Neumann for 2D CAs), whether to consider the state of the cell itself or not (totalistic and outer-totalistic, respectively) and whether it is necessary to search for a mirrored neighborhood (isotropic). Besides, CAs can also be defined on irregular topologies such as networks [6, 11, 12]. In the latter case, due to the network heterogeneity, the rule space needs to be defined according to the network connectivity (degree) [6–8].

The Life-like network automaton (LLNA) [8] is an interesting 2-state CA that was introduced recently and is inspired by the classic Life-like CA. The transition function takes into account the neighborhood density (ρ_i), which is defined as the ratio of the number of neighboring cells that are alive to the total number of neighbors of a given cell. As a consequence, this makes that all the rules in the family of 2D Life-like CA can be implemented as a LLNA as well.

Proposed mainly as a pattern recognition tool, the LLNA framework considers that every rule is a potential solution for a specific classification problem. Therefore, for each different application every single rule must be evaluated for what concerns its performance in terms of classification accuracy. Consequently, the size of the rule space together with the network dimension have a big impact on the computing time.

A large rule space can give the impression that many solutions are available, but a huge rule space may not always guarantee a better solution. Still, in many cases, the rule space needs to be constrained in order to make it possible to handle huge datasets. For the LLNA family, we found that increasing the number of partitions of the neighborhood density (ρ_i) above the mean degree of the network will not influence the final classification performance.

The concern of this work is to present how the rule space can be reduced for a family of CAs defined on a network. Those CAs will be called as network automata (NAs). The transition function of such NAs uses the neighborhood density of the given cells to define their states during the NA evolution, and, the partition of the neighborhood density will depend on the average degree of the underlying network.

In Section 2 we present the family of NAs characterized by the neighborhood density. We start with the definition of the LLNA and then we present how their neighborhoods can be generalized to other NAs. In Section 3 we present a canonical analysis in order to find the best separation among networks generated according to four different families, namely, random, small-world, scale-free and geographic. Finally, in Section 4 we present the final considerations.

2 Network automata defined by neighborhood density

In this paper, we define a network automaton (NA) as a quintuple $\mathcal{C} = \langle \mathcal{T}, \mathbb{S}, s_0, \mathcal{N}, \phi \rangle$, where, (i) \mathcal{T} is the network topology comprising a set \mathcal{V} of nodes and a set \mathcal{E} of edges; (ii) \mathbb{S} is the set of states; (iii) s_0 is the configuration of all the cells $c_i \in \mathcal{T}$ at time $t = 0$; (iv) \mathcal{N} is the neighborhood relationship given by the adjacency matrix A , where $A_{ij} = 1$ if $e_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}$, and $A_{ij} = 0$ otherwise, and, ϕ is the transition function that gives the state of each cell c_i at time t . Throughout this paper, the words “node” and “cell” are used interchangeably. The transition functions of the NAs explored here account for the proportion of the neighborhood elements that are in a specific state. Therefore, for what concerns the states of the nodes, working with the neighborhood density makes it possible to handle non-uniform distributions of network nodes. In the following

sections, we describe the LLNA proposed in [8] and the generalization of these to different rule spaces.

2.1 Life-like Network Automata

The (LLNA) [8] is inspired by the two-dimensional Life-like CA and was first proposed in a pattern recognition framework [4, 8], and extended to other fields, such as cryptography [3]. For each classic 2D Life-like CA rule there exists a corresponding rule that uniquely characterizes the evolution of a network automaton. Therefore, the same vast rule space exists for LLNA.

Specifically for LLNA, \mathbb{S} consists of two elements, such that $s_i = 0$ represents the “dead” state and $s_i = 1$ the “alive” state. The degree of node i is defined as $k_i = \sum_{j=1}^N A_{ij}$, where N is the number of nodes. Since k_i varies throughout the network, the neighborhood density (ρ_i) is used to keep track of the number of neighbors in the “alive” state:

$$\rho_i = \frac{1}{k_i} \sum_{j=1}^N A_{ij} s_j(t), \tag{1}$$

where $s_j(t)$ is the state of node j at time t .

For what concerns the transition function ϕ , a LLNA can be characterized by the same notation employed to represent the classic Life-like CAs: Bx/Sy , where x and y are sets such that $x = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n | x_i \in \mathbb{N}, 0 \leq x_i \leq 8\}$, $y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m | y_i \in \mathbb{N}, 0 \leq y_i \leq 8\}$. B and S stands for “birth” and “survival”, therefore, the numbers in x and y sets represent the possible numbers of neighbors alive so that a cell can be born (going to state 0 to 1) or survive (stay in state 1). Therefore, B and S may contain from zero up to nine elements from $\{0, \dots, 8\}$, e.g. B3/S23. Finally, ϕ can be defined as

$$\phi_i(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \begin{cases} \phi_i(t) = 0 \text{ and } \sum_{j=1}^{|B|} h_i^{x_j}(t) > 0 \\ \phi_i(t) = 1 \text{ and } \sum_{j=1}^{|S|} h_i^{y_j}(t) > 0 \end{cases} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

where $h_i^{x_j}(t)$ and $h_i^{y_j}(t)$ map the correspondence between x and y in the Life-like rule Bx/Sy , and, the density ρ_i , for each cell belonging to the NA, according to

$$h_i^x(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \frac{x}{R} \leq \rho_i < \frac{x+1}{R} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \tag{3}$$

where $R = 9$ for the LLNA. The conditions for survival can be verified through the same function by just replacing x by y in $h_i^y(t)$. In order to illustrate such approach, consider for instance rule B3/S23. In this case, a node i is born if three neighbors are alive ($x = \{3\}$), then $h_i^3(t)$ must be equal to 1, while a node i will survive if $h_i^2(t) = 1$ or $h_i^3(t) = 1$.

2.2 Generalization to other neighborhoods

In this section, we extend the definition of LLNA to different partitions of the neighborhood density ρ_i , that is bounded by a parameter R . For LLNA, the birth and survival conditions (Bx/Sy) are defined for $R = 9$. Therefore, in this specific case, there are nine intervals of the form $\left[\frac{u}{9}, \frac{u+1}{9}\right[= \left\{ \rho_i \in \mathbb{R} \mid \frac{u}{9} \leq \rho_i < \frac{u+1}{9} \right\}$ for $u \in x$, in the case of birth or $u \in y$, for survival. This is since it uses the Moore neighborhood. As such, the parameter R is used for partitioning the density interval according to the number of neighbors, which can be done not only to simulate the Moore neighborhood, but also to generalize the concept to other NA families. So, we can define a family of NA parametrized by the number of partitions of the density interval R . These partitions are

$$\left[\frac{u}{R}, \frac{u+1}{R}\right[= \left\{ \rho_i \in \mathbb{R}, \mid \frac{u}{R} \leq \rho_i < \frac{u+1}{R} \right\}, \quad (4)$$

with $R > 2$. Fig. 1(a) presents a schematic representation of the partitioning of the density range. As R increases, the number of combinations Bx/Sy that can be represented in the rule space also increases. Therefore, more details can be captured from the spatio-temporal pattern of the NAs. However, the total number of rules, n , grows exponentially as $n \sim 2^{2R}$ (Fig. 1(b)). Consequently, it becomes difficult to explore rule spaces defined by large values of R .

3 Results and Discussion

In this paper, we investigated four different types of network topologies and how these affect the spatio-temporal attributes of the NAs. The first is the random network generated according to the Erdős & Rényi model [2], which is parametrized by the probability (p) of connection between two network nodes. The second type is the small-world network, generated according to the model of Watts & Strogatz [13]. The third network model is the scale-free network [1], which presents a power-law distribution of the degree of the nodes. Finally, the last network topology investigated here is the geographic network, which is a spatial model and, therefore, the properties concerning the connectivity of the network are related to the spatial position of the network nodes [9].

The dataset used in our simulations are composed by networks generated according to the four models described above. In addition, the networks have the following mean degree $\langle k \rangle$: 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16, and, the following values for the number of nodes: N : 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000. In total, there are 30 networks for each combination $\langle k \rangle$ - N -network model, resulting in 3360 networks.

We simulated the evolution of the NA family, parametrized by R and described in the previous section for the sample networks. The number of partitions R was varied between 2 and 9. In order to quantitatively assess the properties of the spatio-temporal patterns obtained from the dynamic evolution of the NAs, we calculated the Shannon entropy (S) for each network node, as follows

Fig. 1. The rule space and the parameter R , which defines a family of NAs. (a) Possible values that x and y can assume for different values of parameter R . There are unique correspondences between the Bx/Sy rule and R . (b) Number of rules as a function of the parameter R .

$S_i = -(p_i^0 \log_2 p_i^0 + p_i^1 \log_2 p_i^1)$, where p_i^0 is the probability of having a zero and p_i^1 the probability of having a one in the time series of the node's state. First, this assessment is done per node. Then, in a second step, the so-called network descriptor, μ_S , is calculated on the basis of the set of all S_i . We define μ_{S_j} as the Shannon entropy distribution for a network j . For a given network, the S_i values are grouped in entropy intervals. Therefore, μ_{S_j} describes the proportion of network nodes having S_i values in a specific entropy range, for network j . Given that S_i can assume values between 0 and 1, we grouped the entropy values in 20 equally spaced intervals.

Considering our dataset, for each network we obtain a descriptor μ_S , which reflects the network characterization based on the spatio-temporal evolution of the NA. Figure 2 presents a canonical analysis thereof in order to evaluate the separation among the four network models given μ_S as a network descriptor. Each circle corresponds to a single network. Each plot presented in this figure corresponds to a different value of R , e.g., the upper-left plot is the result of the NA with $R = 2$, for rule B1/S1. For this example, we have 16 possible rules given by the combination of 0, 1 and the empty set for B and for S, as follows: B/S, B/S0, B/S1, B/S01, B0/S, B0/S0, B0/S1, B0/S01, B1/S, B1/S0, B1/S1, B1/S01, B01/S, B01/S0, B01/S1 and B01/S01. The other plots in Fig. 2 were generated in a similar way with rules B1/S, B1/S0, B123/S0124,

Fig. 2. Canonical analysis performed for the four network models using μ_S as network descriptor. Each value of R corresponds to a density-based network automaton. The scale-free, random, small-world and geographic networks are represented, respectively, by the blue, purple, green and red dots small circles.

B1345/S34, B03456/S234, B0167/S356 and B01678/S0457 respectively. The rule sets for each $R = 3, 4, \dots, 9$ can be derived in the same way as defined above for $R = 2$. The choice of the rule to be used for each specific R was carried out through the same procedure as described for the LLNA method which consists in splitting the dataset in two parts, one for the validation and the other one for testing the classifier performance (cross-validation). The k-NN classifier was used to classify the network model using the network descriptors obtained for each network (μ_{S_j}). Therefore, the classification performance is quantified based on the number of networks that were correctly labeled.

We can observe from Fig. 2 that as R increases, the separation between the network types becomes clearer. For $R = 6$, it is already possible to obtain a good separation among the network models, which is not observed for $R \leq 4$. Besides being generated according to different theoretical models, the networks are heterogeneous for what concerns their mean degree ($\langle k \rangle$) and the number of nodes (N). As pointed out in [8], the influence of the latter on the final network descriptor is marginal considering networks of the same class, however, regarding $\langle k \rangle$, the connectivity may have a higher influence on μ_S . As a network gets more connections, $\langle k \rangle$ increases and it turns out to be more difficult to distinguish between two network types.

Another important characteristic is that as R increases, more details can be obtained from the dynamical evolution of the NA. However, if R is larger than $\langle k \rangle$, the final performance is not affected, and, therefore, a small R may be used. It is also important to note that a rule of the form Bx/Sy , where $x = 2$, for instance, is not the same rule for different values of R , since the partitions of the neighborhood density are not the same. This implies that different values of R must be investigated.

4 Conclusion

In this work we evaluated what is the optimal/recommended rule space for classifying classes of networks generated according to different theoretical models. The results obtained so far show that the separation among those classes depends on the average degree $\langle k \rangle$. However, a detailed analysis to investigate the relationship between the dimension of the rule space and the classification accuracy, for what concerns the correct identification of the network classes, must be conducted in future.

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